

Reductimetric Titration of Methylene Blue, Thionine, Nitroso-R-Salt, 1-Nitroso-2-Naphthol and 2-Nitroso-1-Naphthol

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Methylene blue, thionine, nitroso-R-salt, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 2-nitroso-1-naphthol can be titrated in 11.5-13M phosphoric acid medium with iron(II) ammonium sulphate.

SO far the direct titration of methylene blue, thionine, nitroso-R-salt, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 2-nitroso-1-naphthol with iron(II) is not tried. Recently Rao and Sagi¹ reported that the formal redox potential of Fe(III)/Fe(II) couple decreases with increase in phosphoric acid concentration. In view of the above observation the authors present in this communication the details of the direct titration of the above mentioned substances with iron(II) in phosphoric acid medium.

Experimental

Reagents: Iron(II) sulphate (0.04N) is prepared in 1N sulphuric acid. Aqueous solutions of 0.01M nitroso-R-salt and methylene blue and 0.004M thionine are prepared and standardised against a standard solution of titanium(III)². 0.1% solutions of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 2-nitroso-1-naphthol in glacial acetic acid are prepared and standardised against titanium(III)².

Procedure: An aliquot of dye solution and syrupy phosphoric acid to give 12M at the equivalence point are taken in a titration vessel and carbon dioxide is passed through the contents for 10 minutes. Then the contents are titrated with iron(II) solution by adding the titrant near the equivalence point slowly to the pale

Thionine	1.077	2.018	1.87
	1.293	2.462	1.90
	1.659	3.127	1.89
	1.754	3.291	1.88
			Average : 1.89
Nitroso-R-Salt	3.961	15.75	3.98
	4.951	19.82	4.00
	7.921	31.50	3.98
	9.902	40.09	4.05
			Average : 4.00
1-Nitroso-2-Naphthol	2.668	10.38	3.89
	3.963	15.26	3.85
	4.623	17.93	3.88
	5.283	20.18	3.82
			Average : 3.86
2-Nitroso-1-Naphthol	3.338	13.68	4.10
	2.225	9.040	4.06
	1.669	6.714	4.02
	1.108	4.457	4.01
			Average : 4.05

TABLE 1

Compound	Compound taken m. moles $\times 10^{-2}$	Fe(II) consumed m. moles $\times 10^{-2}$	Moles of Fe(II) Moles of compound
Methylene Blue	6.106	13.33	2.18
	7.734	17.04	2.20
	8.141	17.74	2.18
	9.158	20.21	2.20
			Average : 2.19

green (in case of methylene blue), to colourless stage (in case of Nitroso-R-salt and 1-nitroso-2-naphthol) to pale brown (in case of 2-nitroso-1-naphthol) and to rose red (in case of thionine). Some representative results from which the mole ratios are established, are presented in table. 1.

Discussion

From the mole ratio considerations it is evident that the dyes are reduced to their corresponding leuco compounds, and the nitroso groups are reduced to their corresponding amino groups in nitroso compounds.

The advantage of the present method as compared with the determination of the compounds with other reductants (V(II), Ti(III), Sn(II) and Cr(II)) is that the titration can be carried out at room temperature and the reagent can be stored in normal volumetric flasks besides that the method is simple.

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References

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